

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY

MODULE III: IMPACT ASSESSMENT MODELS AND THEIR USE IN CAP STRATEGIC PLANS

3 December 2024

The third [Tools4CAP](#) (*Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions*) [Academy](#) module took place on 3 December 2024. The event gathered 50 attendees from different backgrounds. See the agenda [here](#).

Tools4CAP's Academy aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer-learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet end users' needs. It seeks to promote [meaningful engagement](#) with stakeholders who may benefit from this project. **This third module aimed to:** (i) contribute to participants gaining knowledge and skills on impact assessment models within the context of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plans; (ii) provide information and examples of how impact assessment models like iMAP, CAPRI, and GLOBIOM are applied in CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs); and (iii) enhance the exchange, learning, and interaction with project end users, which include EU, national, and local policy-makers, as well as governance bodies.

During that training session, two presentations were made by [Ecorys](#), as project coordinator, and [AEIDL](#), as Academy coordinator, addressing the following points:

- Presentation of the project, its usefulness for improving the design and monitoring of the national CSPs, and current results.
- Explanation of the objectives, activities, and the upcoming development of the project Academy.

The session included four presentations on:

- [Perspectives on Impact Assessment Models – the iMAP project](#) introduced by Thomas Fellmann from the EU Joint Research Centre.
- [GLOBIOM model](#) presented by Juliana Arbelaez-Gaviria of Czechglobe/IIASA and Amanda Palazzo and Petr Havlík from IIASA.
- [CAPRI modelling system](#) explained by Peter Witzke from EuroCARE.
- [CAPRI modelling exercise: Hungarian case study](#) presented by Zsolt Szabó from AKI Institute of Agricultural Economics.

The Academy training session, facilitated by Blanca Casares (AEIDL), concluded with a series of next steps, including that the meeting materials and the report on the main elements discussed will be available on the [event page](#) and the [YouTube channel](#). This highlights report will be translated into 16 EU languages covered by the consortium.

ORGANISER:

3 DECEMBER 2024

ONLINE

50 PARTICIPANTS

(EU institutions; public authorities at national and regional level; researchers; innovators; farmers; and other stakeholders relevant to the agricultural sector)

21 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

If you see this icon, click to see the video

ACADEMY SESSIONS

The Tools4CAP project

Bérénice Dupeux

Tools4CAP project's coordination (Ecorys)

Bérénice Dupeux (Ecorys) presented the [Tools4CAP](#) project, which is a Coordination and Support Action in Horizon Europe (2023-2026) coordinated by [Ecorys](#), gathering 21 [partner organisations](#). The project aims to support the design and monitoring of the current national CSPs and lay the foundations for sound preparation of post-2027 Strategic Plans through a bottom-up adaptation of innovative methods and tools.

She began by giving an overview of the main beneficiaries of the project, and continued by explaining the approach to be followed in the upcoming years and the expected main outcomes throughout the project.

- **End users:** policy-makers (EU, national and regional) and governance bodies.
- **Universities, researchers and young scientists.**
- **Innovators and developers.**
- **Farmers, producers and producers' associations.**
- **Other stakeholders** relevant to agricultural and rural development.

Tools4CAP beneficiaries

Tools4CAP key outcomes

She presented the [inventory](#) of methods and tools used in the 27 Member States and introduced the 10 [case studies](#) to be developed in the coming months. She concluded by showcasing the latest key reports available online: (i) [Evaluation of methods and tools](#); (ii) [Assessment of the potential of innovative modelling tools](#); (iii) [Key challenges for decision-making across EU Member States](#); (iv) [Integration of farm level data towards CAP monitoring and evaluation](#); and (v) [Challenges and approaches for landscape monitoring](#).

ACADEMY SESSIONS

Tools4CAP Academy

Blanca Casares

Policy expert and project manager (AEIDL)

Blanca Casares (AEIDL) introduced the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), coordinated by [AEIDL](#) in close collaboration with other project partners. The Academy provides a framework for capacity building and peer-learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme composed of 10 modules to meet the end users' needs. It aims to:

- Strengthen end user capacity to use innovative methods and tools.
- Facilitate the sharing of results and the exchange of knowledge and best practices.

Tools4CAP Academy modules plan

The results will be consolidated into a Capacity Building Toolkit, which will be translated into 16 EU languages.

In her presentation, Blanca reviewed [Module I](#), which focused on the project's inventory of methods and tools and was organised on 17 January 2024, as well as [Module II](#) on advanced data management and monitoring for CAP Strategic Plans, held on 20 November 2024.

In addition, Blanca explained other activities of the Academy, such as collecting experts' insights through interviews or blog articles, tools factsheets, and joint actions with other projects or networks. She also introduced a dedicated section on the project's website

called [Practical Information for CSP](#). It includes relevant documents, from the legal framework, to the approved national CSPs, and key sources for implementation, evaluation and innovation.

The information and materials from the modules will be available in the [specific section](#) of the website, as well as on the event page and [YouTube channel](#).

The project provides the possibility to get involved in different activities: [focus groups](#), [case studies](#), interviews, surveys, training sessions and dissemination efforts. The [consent form](#) is available on the website.

Perspectives on Impact Assessment Models - the iMAP project

Thomas Fellmann

EU Joint Research Centre (JRC)

Thomas Fellmann (JRC) provided an introductory overview of the perspectives on impact assessment models. He presented the integrated Modelling Platform for Agro-economic and Resource Policy Analysis (**iMAP**) focusing on the EU baseline construction process.

On the construction process, Thomas reflected on the development of the baseline and the challenges involved. The external drivers to be considered, the assumptions for these external drivers, as well as the main agricultural production and market developments are determined in the process of the EU Agricultural Medium-Term Outlook.

He concluded by presenting the modelling needs and capacities, focusing on key areas for development and integration:

- Expanding individual models.
- Integrating models across different levels: (i) linking socio-economic, biophysical, and environmental models with other approaches, and (ii) developing additional tools and models to enhance and extend the analysis.

Integrated policy analysis based on the core iMAP models

Following the presentation, the moderator posed a question regarding the primary challenges in interpreting or utilising iMAP results. Thomas responded by emphasising that it is challenging to reflect the CAP Strategic Plans in the modelling because the current Plans vary significantly across Europe, reflecting diverse national priorities.

Another participant inquired about exiting models to quantify the impacts of CAP Strategic Plans at the national

and regional levels. Thomas explained that a detailed understanding requires integration with farm-level models. He noted that the actual implementation levels of certain interventions or schemes still remains unknown. Models can provide insights into the potential uptake of schemes based on profit maximisation, offering a way to assess the appropriateness of specific interventions and inform policy decisions.

IMPACT ASSESSMENT MODELS

GLOBIOM model

Juliana Arbelaez-Gaviria, Amanda Palazzo and Petr Havlik

International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)

Juliana Arbelaez-Gaviria and Amanda Palazzo, both working at IIASA, presented the Global Biosphere Management Model known as **GLOBIOM**. Developed by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), this model is widely used for policy analysis, particularly in the context of climate change, food security, and sustainable development.

GLOBIOM is a partial-equilibrium economic land use model. It covers the market demand and supply of agricultural and forestry sector products which allows the model to be used for assessing global and regional land-use competition. It incorporates international trade,

including bilateral trade flows using a spatial equilibrium approach. The model accounts for land use and land-use change dynamics over time, and is run on a decadal time step from 2000 up to 2100.

Following the introduction to the model, they discussed its use in the Czech Republic's national CAP Strategic Plan. Notably, 39% of the total national CAP budget is dedicated to interventions targeting environmental and climate goals. They also highlighted the application of GLOBIOM to the ex-ante analysis of the by 2024. In this context, the model's outputs supports the response to the **PMEF** result indicators such as R12, R13, R14, R17, R22, R23, R29, R30, R31.

The outputs includes:

- GHG emissions from crop and livestock production as well as land-use changes, incorporating both planned and autonomous adaptation measures.
- Fertiliser application rates and water use, covering domestic, industrial, and irrigation purposes.
- Land use patterns and land-use changes over time.

In their final remarks, Juliana and Amanda highlighted that ex-ante modelling tools like GLOBIOM help quantify potential futures for the national agricultural sector, aligning with EU targets and aiding stakeholders in evaluating synergies and trade-offs. The Scenario Explorer provides detailed insights into national and European-level outcomes for agriculture and forestry, supporting informed policymaking within a globally consistent framework.

One participant asked how to use the model to quantify the impact of the CAP Strategic Plans. Juliana explained that a single model is not the answer, but that the integration of several models is necessary. GLOBIOM allows to support the strategic planning and evaluation of the **specific objectives of the CAP** 4, 5 and 6. It also provides greater accuracy in the data used, and the calibration and validation period utilise data from FAOstat, Eurostat, iMAP reference base, and others.

GLOBIOM Framework

CAPRI modelling system

Peter Witzke and Guna Salputra

EuroCARE

Zsolt Szabó

AKI Institute of Agricultural Economics

Peter Witzke (EuroCARE) introduced the [CAPRI](#) (Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact) modelling system as a robust analytical framework designed to evaluate the impacts of agricultural and environmental policies within the EU. It features core characteristics such as detailed economic and environmental modeling capabilities. The system's development has consistently evolved to address policy challenges, ensuring its relevance for contemporary decision-making.

CAPRI relies on a comprehensive database, incorporating key inputs and outputs related to agricultural production, trade, and environmental factors. It integrates policy inputs specific to the CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs), facilitating tailored analysis for policy evaluation. Additionally, CAPRI provides a clear understanding of baseline conditions and policy scenarios, enabling detailed comparisons and informed policy decisions. Peter highlighted that in “baseline mode” CAPRI modelling system is more a statistical projection tool than an economic model.

Peter provided the CAP interventions (direct and rural development support) included in the CAPRI policy module. The data needed to quantify CSPs for modelling is available through the JRC-prepared [master file](#), and their integration is currently being implemented in a dedicated “branch” of CAPRI. This functionality is expected to be incorporated into the standard version (“Trunk”) by 2025, enabling the standard version to also simulate potential modifications or revisions of national CSPs.

Finally, Peter gave an overview of the applications in earlier ex-ante impact assessments for the European Commission, highlighting its effectiveness in simulating policy impacts in DG AGRI, DG SANTE and DG CLIMA.

CAPRI scenario exercise example

Zsolt Szabó (Institute of Agricultural Economics - AKI) presented hypothetical scenarios that simulated the response to *How would the withdrawal of coupled support for milk across the EU influence farmers' and policy-makers' opinions on the CAP?*

Among other considerations, Zsolt pointed out that CAPRI focuses on direct payments (known as first pillar payments). Payments from the Second Pillar and national payments were not modified in this exercise.

Furthermore, he focused on some concrete specifications of the use of the model in an analysis of the Hungarian dairy sector support as well as the national Strategic Plan.

PLENARY DISCUSSIONS

Participants and speakers from the Academy module on impact assessment models

At the end of the presentations, participants had a plenary discussion time where two questions were asked:

Q: Can the CAPRI model be used for ex-post analysis or during implementation for control purposes?

A: The model is traditionally designed for ex-ante assessments but could potentially be adapted to evaluate what might have happened without the policies. However, this would require significant modifications to the model and data, as its primary focus remains on ex-ante analysis.

Q: How can the model be used to assess the impact of specific CAP measures?

A: We need more impact analysis of CAP strategic plans to create credible scenarios. This requires ensuring data availability, aligning with the pace of the policy cycle, gaining a better understanding of the CAP interventions, and maintaining ongoing engagement with the results.

In closing the event Blanca Casares (AEIDL) thanked the audience and reminded recordings, presentations and this Highlights report will be available in the coming days on the [event page](#) and the [YouTube channel](#). This highlights report will be soon translated into 16 EU languages covered by the consortium.

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

Get involved in the project, [here](#).

Or sign up for the newsletter, [here](#).

New training modules of the Academy will be published in the near future, [here](#).

TOOLS 4 CAP

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